

PUBLIC DEBTS AND INFLATION IN NIGERIA: AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION

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Abstract

The study was conducted with a view to examining the effect of public debts on inflation in Nigeria. The study period spanned 2000-2021. An ex-post facto research design with the use of time series data was employed for the study. Public debt was disaggregated into domestic debts and external debts while inflation was the rate of inflation as reported by the CBN statistical bulletin. Ordinary least square (OLS) estimation technique in linear form was used in estimating the study model. Findings showed that there is a negative non-significant relationship between domestic debts and inflation and a positive significant relationship between external debts and inflation in Nigeria for the studied period. The conclusion is that, domestic debt can be a very important tool in controlling inflation in Nigeria while external debts could be used in promoting investment in critical infrastructure and development. From the findings, it is recommended that government should consider the use of domestic debts as a tool for controlling inflation while external debts should only be considered when infrastructural development is necessary. In addition, there should be proper institutional framework to ensure effective management of public debts.

Keywords: Public Debt, Debt Management, Inflation, Hyperinflation, Economic Growth.

1. INTRODUCTION

There is constant debate across academic and government corners on topics of macroeconomic management and public finance. At the very fore of these debates is the important issue of public debt. Debt generally either by private organizations or public organizations is an obligation to the debtor and imposes a burden of repayment to the debtor either wholly or partially in some time in the future. Besides imposing a burden of repayment to the debtor, Edeminam (2021) asserts that, there are benefits associated with debt, among which are; the provision of immediate bulk cash necessary for capital-intensive projects, the cost of which projects will tighten the fiscal space in the economy if sourced from government coffers. Furthermore, debt allows the government to undertake countercyclical fiscal policy in times of economic recession. Other forms of debt such as venture capital and project finances make execution of projects faster as the undue bureaucratic bottlenecks associated

with the processing of debt is removed by these forms of financing. In view of the perceived benefits of debt, it is obvious that mismanagement of debt is detrimental to the economy as it creates debt traps capable of straining limited resources for extended periods of time (Filip, 2019). Also, rising debt could lead to uncertainty among citizens about the economic outlook in the future because of expectations of future tax increases and government expenditure cuts in order to repay the debt.

Though debt can be incurred by both private and public sector organizations to finance their projects, it is essential to point out that the current study is specifically concerned with public debt as it impacts on inflation in Nigeria. Public debt is the obligation of the government of a country towards individuals, organizations, countries, entities or communities of lenders within and outside the country. As the name implies, public debt is debt incurred by the government of a state from her nationals or organizations within her border and from nationals and organizations outside her border. The former is known as domestic debt while the latter is the foreign debt. Both domestic and foreign debt collectively constitutes public debt.

Onyele and Nwadike (2021) note that, public debt is of macroeconomic importance because it helps provide investible funds, reduce budget constraint by making funds available to finance balance of payment and fiscal deficits. Nations, especially resource-scarce economies, borrow to improve capital formation and investments, which are often deterred by the lack of domestic savings (The World Bank, 2020). From the perspective of the dual gap of growth theory, debt is often inevitable because foreign exchange earnings and savings necessary to finance domestic investments are not usually adequate, especially in developing countries. However, poor management of national debt could cause financial distress and economic crisis in the debtor country due to debt servicing (Sosvilla-Rivero and Gomez-Puig, 2019; Onyele and Nwadike, 2020).

The use of debt as a source of financing no doubt has its benefits as well as its cost. When an entity borrows, there is always the marginal cost of funds which invariably could result in crowding out private investment. Again, the borrowed fund when used in financing deficits could have an expansionary effect on the economy. Expansionary fiscal policy increases aggregate demand and may eventually result in inflation. The extent to which public debt influences other macroeconomic variables in the economy is a function of how the borrowed fund is managed.

Aiyedogbon *et al.* (2022), note that due to scarcity of resources especially in developing economies, borrowing becomes an alternative to fast-track investment and capital formation. Agreeably, borrowing provides funds for investments as well as financing deficits in the balance of payments. However, it should be admitted that, persistent and growing deficit financing through public debt will eventually produce inflationary pressure regardless of policy adopted by the monetary authority (Muhummad *et al.*, 2021).

There has been consistent debate on the relationship between public debt and inflation in Nigeria. Some people believe that as long as the debt is being judiciously utilized, it will result in the good of all. Thus, the effective use of loans can become a positive factor in economic development. Consequently, an excessive and uncontrolled use of public debt in funding fiscal deficit portends a very grave danger on the national economy (Zhuravka *et al.*, 2021).

It is important that the claim on the public debt-inflation nexus be further examined in view of the Nigeria rising debt profile. A snapshot of the Nigeria debt profile between 2021 and 2022 by the National Bureau for Statistics (NBS, 2022), indicates that, Nigeria's public debt stock, which includes external and domestic debt, rose by 20.81 percent between the second quarter of 2021 and the second quarter of 2022, driven by weak naira, rising inflation and revenue leakages. This represented an increase to N42.84 trillion (\$ 103.31 billion) in the second quarter of 2022 from N35.46 trillion (\$86.57 billion) of the same period in 2021. A breakdown of the public debt shows that external debt rose from N13.71 trillion (\$33.46 billion) in Q2 2021 to N16.61 trillion (\$40.06 billion) in Q2 2022. The domestic debt increased to N26.23 trillion (\$63.24 billion) in Q2 2022 from N21.75 trillion (\$53.10 billion) in the same period last year.

One of the contributors to the increase in the debt figures is an increase in inflation rate, especially the general increase in the price of the things the government is spending money on, according to Ayodele Akinwunmi, relationship manager, corporate banking at FSDH Merchant Bank Limited. Other factors, according to him, are the depreciation in the value of the naira, leading to increase in the local prices of imported goods, coupled with its ripple effects on the prices of other locally made goods, and revenue leakages, which make borrowing an alternative to meet certain expenses. The proposed revenue and expenditure budgets for 2023 are N9.73 trillion and N20.51 trillion, respectively, resulting in a N10.78 trillion fiscal deficit, which represents 4.78 percent of GDP.

There is a growing gap between revenue and expenditure, and the gap has been widening and also reflecting in the growth of the fiscal deficit. There is a projection of N9.73 trillion revenues but the trend over the past has been revenue underperformance. This has created a huge gap for funding and it has to be filled by borrowing. That is why the debt has been increasing – the regular debt, treasury bills, bond, foreign borrowing and the one that has not been captured – the Ways and Means Advances. Nigeria's rising public debt is driven majorly by the huge budget deficits, especially in the past few years. Expenditure is growing but revenue is not growing. What this means for the economy is that, a sustained rise in public debt amid low revenue profile may affect the country's sovereign credit rating, making it even more difficult and costly to borrow with concomitant implications for the private sector and the broader economy.

Implication of rising government debts, which are largely non-self-liquidating, is increase in debt burden, which manifests in unsustainable debt service ratios. The huge debt service obligations come with huge opportunity costs as they crowd out funds that could have been applied to critical sectors of the economy. For example, in the 2023 proposed budget, a whopping N6.3 trillion is appropriated for debt service alone – an amount higher than the capital provision of about N5.4 trillion.

Ideally, public debt should be measured in real terms rather than nominal term. Therefore, budget deficit should always be corrected for inflation. Public debt follows business cycle, which means that during recession public debt usually increase; while during boom it reduces. Public debt has expansionary effects on an economy when the debt is spent on public work; this is because it will lead to inflation and other consequential negative effects (Shuaibu *et al.*, 2021). There are a lot of debates about the long-term effect of debt; some see it as a burden on future generation, others argued otherwise. The extent to which these debate influences the present and the future in terms of consumer perception is worth examining. The essence of this study is to do exactly that.

In the public sector, debt plays vital role in providing the finance and enabling resources to achieve the common good. Consequently, debt can be used as an instrument of stabilization. This in because, during recession, government uses borrowing to finance deficit and this has an expansionary effect on the economy. Public debt (domestic) is also believed to be a tool of controlling inflation. This is achieved through collecting money from the hands of the public who purchase government bonds. But, the money use in government expenditure can result in creating inflationary condition. Deficit financing raises aggregate demand in relation to aggregate supply, thereby leading to inflationary rise in prices. At the same time, when government repays its internal debt to the public, it leads to increase in the money supply with the public. The resulting effect of this may be increase in aggregate demand.

The inflationary effect of government borrowing may be helpful to business in times of depression, but it contributes to high prices in times of prosperity or war. But borrowing from individuals through issuance of bond by government is not considered inflationary according to this reasoning. The effect is opposite i.e., deflationary; because it leads to less money in the hand of individuals and hence less purchasing power. But when the government spends the money it has borrowed, the deflationary effect is cancelled. By borrowing from the domestic market, government is crowding out private investments as the cost of borrowing increase in the process.

Borrowing may stimulate economic activities both in the short run and in the long run. At the same time, it may impose heavy burden on the economy due to the fact that it represents a drag on the economy owing to accrual of interest rate. Apart from

financing fiscal deficits via borrowing from domestic and external sources, other options include quantitative easing (QE) and withdrawal from the country's external reserves (Nya & Onyimadu 2019). In Nigeria and other developing nations, quantitative easing is not a recommended for deficit financing owing to the fact that these are consumption-based nations and the employment of quantitative easing in the long run could lead to hyperinflation as a result of a rise in money supply. Printing of money is extremely inflationary as a rise in the volume of money does not correspond to a rise in productive activities in the economy. For most part, these constant deficits had been financed by the government via borrowing from internal or external sources, and from time to time through external reserves reduction.

If borrowing is undertaken to promote public works, this would have guaranteed increase in productive activities, generate employment, reduce poverty as well as positioned the economy on the path of growth and development. The fact that borrowing is undertaken for consumption has a dilapidating effect on the economy. It should be noted that debt whether domestic or foreign is incurred at a cost that must be repaid now or in the future. The repayment no doubt has the effect of eroding the purchasing power of the citizenry. While some believe that the effect of public debt on the economy is inflationary, others take the position that, the effect is deflationary. These two positions are predicated on the fact that, inflation is a monetary phenomenon and as a monetary phenomenon, increase in money supply is likely to bring about inflationary pressure and vice-versa. The extent to which these arguments hold is worth re-examining. Hence, the essence of this study. Generally, this study is set to examine the effect of public debt on inflation. Specifically, the study seeks to examine the effect of domestic debt on inflation and to examine the effect of foreign debt on inflation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Government, like individuals and businesses, borrow to attend to its economic and financial needs. By borrowing, government incurs public debt which simply means borrowing from the public. Public debt also known as government debt, National debt or sovereign debt is the aggregate amount of money that government owes either to her citizens and/or local financial organisations (domestic debt) or foreign financial organisations (external debt). Any form of government debt imposes a debt burden which is the financial crisis or distress arising from debt repayment due to constant interest payment from government revenue and foreign reserves Onyele and Nwadike, 2021).

Ngangnchi, Joefendeh, and Innocent (2022), are of the opinion that, the principal reason for government borrowing is to finance public goods that increase welfare and promote economic growth. Earlier, Shuaibu *et al.* (2021), assert that, government borrows for the purpose of economic development such as need for long term planning to finance infrastructural build up. When government spends more than it receives it has a budget deficit; the accumulation of past borrowing is the government

debt. The issue of national debt is not usually taken lightly. While government spending may be financed principally from taxation, debt financing is inevitable as some economies especially the developing economies lack the resources to finance their expenditure. It is imperative that while borrowing to finance their expenditure, developing countries should only borrow when the marginal product of capital is higher than the world interest rate. However, what had been noticed over time is that instead of improving their economies through the borrowed funds, most countries in Africa plunge deeper into more debt and the cost of servicing such debts plunge their already impoverished economies into debt overhang.

Kaka (2021) asserts that, lack of adequate generation of tax revenue and non-tax revenue to finance government expenditure, lead to continuous increase in budget deficit in Nigeria and other nation of the world. Thus, for the government to breach the gap between revenue and expenditure, government has to resort to borrowing to finance the deficit. Over the years, the government of Nigeria has obtained different kinds of loan locally and internationally from both national and international financial institutions, foreign governments to finance developmental projects in the government efforts to breach the gaps of deficit in its budget (Rahmon, 2018). With Nigeria achieving debt cancellation from communities of lenders in 2005, one would have thought that Nigeria's debt problem was over. However, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) (2018) reported that, in 2011, internal and external public debt figures at the national and sub national levels stood at the manageable threshold of N11,205 trillion in 2016, N34,319 trillion in 2018.

Omesi, Nkak and Orlu (2021), reported that, in 2015 the debt was \$9.7 billion and in 2020 the debt profile rose to \$27 billion. The debts were incurred by the current administration to finance multilateral, development bilateral and so on. Unfortunately, the accumulation of debts for a long time always leads to persistent budget deficit. Financing the interest, public debt and the increasing demand to provide infrastructures, social services and other expenditures without generating enough revenue, can subsequently, leads to more public debt accumulation, which the economy cannot be able to sustain. This issue may further aggravate and increase the problem in the economy, especially in terms of rising interest rate, high associate poverty level, high exchange rate, inflation, economic depression and fiscal crisis (Kiminyei, 2018).

Onyele and Nwadike (2021), remark that, in Nigeria, deficit financing has led to borrowings from richer countries, multinational finance institutions, such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank, African Development Bank (ADB) amongst others. Unfortunately, the rising national debt in Nigeria has begun to outweigh the country's revenue generation capacity and drawing down on foreign reserves, hence stifling the much-needed public capital investments and economic productivity. In Nigeria, deficit financing has led to borrowings from richer countries, multinational finance institutions, such as the International Monetary

Fund (IMF), the World Bank, African Development Bank (ADB) amongst others. Unfortunately, the rising national debt in Nigeria has begun to outweigh the country's revenue generation capacity and drawing down on foreign reserves, hence stifling the much-needed public capital investments and economic productivity. Also, it has been reported that these borrowed funds are often mismanaged and siphoned by public officers, hence, are not used for economically productive activities, leading to debt burden, capital flight and economic instability in the long run.

The use of government revenue to finance interest payments on public debt directly hinders the disposable income and domestic savings in the indebted country. Similarly, mismanagement of debt is detrimental to the economy as it creates debt traps capable of straining limited resources for extended periods of time (Fillip, 2019). Also, rising debt could lead to uncertainty among citizens about the economic outlook in the future because of expectations of future tax increases and government expenditure cuts in order to repay the debt (Edeminam, 2021).

Thus, economies facing debt crisis have to face many challenges. Debt overhang depresses investment and economic growth in an economy. As the size of the public debt increases, the uncertainty about government's actions and policies to meet its debt servicing obligations also increase (Serrao, 2016.)

This study is based on three theories: Lerner's theory of functional finance; Classical theory of public debt and Keynes' theory on public debt.

Lerner's theory of functional finance, put forward by Lerner (1943), is based on the principle of judging fiscal measures based on their function in the economy, called functional finance. This theory suggests that the government should keep the spending rate on expenditure (aggregate demand) within the rate of aggregate supply to avoid inflation or unemployment. To ensure that the required total spending level is achieved, the government can implement either an expansionary or a restrictive fiscal policy.

Classical theory of public debt is drawn from the theoretical concept of laissez-faire, which is also known as the free-market theory. This theory is championed by the classical economists who shared a common principle with regards to public debt, expenditure and revenue, namely Adam Smith and John Stuart Mill. Smith (1937) in *The Wealth of Nations* argues that the accumulation of debt due to budget deficits is to be considered pernicious for the nation even if all of it is owed to domestic investors, and should therefore be avoided. This is supported by Mill (1979) in his principles, arguing, however, that public debt might not be pernicious to a country if financed from foreign savings. This means that there is no crowding out effect when government borrowings absorb domestic savings that would either be invested unproductively or invested in foreign countries.

Contrary to the classical theory is the Keynesian theory on public debt by John Maynard Keynes. Keynes (1936) concurs that the growth of any economy can be stimulated by increased government expenditures and lower taxes; and that governments use fiscal policies in times of recession to improve economic activities. However, governments would cut taxes and increase expenditure to stimulate aggregate demand in times of depression.

The above theories all have conflicting views in an attempt to confirm the relationship between government revenue, expenditure and public debt. Some theories assume that causality runs from revenue to spending, while others urge that government spending increases or decreases government revenue. From the above, the Keynesian theory on public debt is expected to be one of the most interesting for a developing economy such as Nigeria. This is because the government may use fiscal policies in times of recession to improve economic activities. The positive relationship expected between the variables can be further related to the positive theory of public expenditure or displacement effect as the increase in government expenditure in a developing economy may lead to insufficient existing levels of revenue, causing public debt accumulation.

Empirical Literature

Serrao (2016) examined the impact of public debt on the economic growth in advanced economies over a period of 1946 to 2009, using an econometric approach. The findings suggested an inverse relationship between public debt and economic growth in advanced economies. The negative effect of public debt was only stronger on the real GDP growth rate in advanced economies when the public debt-to-GDP ratio is above 220%.

Paul (2017) analysed the impact of external debt on economic growth of Nigeria. Data for the study were collected from secondary sources. The variables on which data were collected include; Gross Domestic Product, External debt services, external debt stock, external reserve, and exchange rate. Data were analysed using the ordinary least square regression. Findings revealed that debt service payment has negative and insignificant impact on Nigeria's economic growth while external debt stock has positive and significant effect on Nigeria's growth index. From the findings, the study recommended that government should apply external loans to infrastructural development; improve business environment through legislation; initiate proper debt management policies and substitute external borrowing for human capital development.

Didia and Ayokunle (2020) examined the impact of public and publicly guaranteed debt on the economic growth of Nigeria. The study disaggregated total public and publicly guaranteed debt into external debt and domestic debt, and examined whether the two kinds of debt have differential impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Utilizing data from the Central Bank of Nigeria, and the World Bank,

empirical analysis using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and covering 1980 – 2016, revealed that domestic debt has a statistically significant positive relationship with economic growth in the long run while external debt exhibited a negative relationship with economic growth was not statistically significant. The lesson here is that domestic debt appears to be more beneficial in terms of economic growth in Nigeria than external debt as interest paid on domestic loans remains in the country and could be put into further productive economic use.

Imosi (2020) examined the relationship between fiscal policy and public debt sustainability in Nigeria within a multivariate framework from 1970–2019. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds test was employed to determine the long run relationship among the variables. The results of the ARDL test revealed that a long run relationship exist between the variables used in the study. Specifically, the result showed that budget deficit has a positive and significant impact on public debt both in the short run and long run, while interest rate, real gross domestic product and inflation rate were statistically insignificant irrespective of the period and thus had no impact on public debt. Thus, it was recommended that the budgeting procedure at the federal and state levels in Nigeria need to re-assessed to make sure that allocative efficiency is achieved in the budgeting system.

Iiyambo, and Kaulihowa (2020) investigated the relationship between government expenditure, government revenue and public debt in Namibia by employing the data of these variables for the period 1980 to 2018. An error correction model (ECM) was employed to analyse the short- run dynamics and a positive relationship between government expenditure and government revenue was found. Similarly, there was supporting evidence that an increase in public debt will stimulate government expenditure. The error correction term indicates that any disequilibrium is corrected at an annual speed of 46.4 percent. Additionally, the pair-wise Granger causality test failed to support the spend-revenue hypothesis.

Edeminam (2021) examined the impact of public debt on economic growth in Nigeria using annual time series data from 1990 to 2019 collected from Central of Nigeria statistical bulletin. The variables were Real GDP, public debt, Inflation, debt to GDP ratio, debt servicing to GDP ratio, and exchange rate. Empirical analysis was conducted using Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test to check for stationarity. Johansen Cointegration test was used to determine long run relationship and Vector Error Correction Model to check for short run and long run impact of public debt on economic growth. Empirical results showed that the impact of public debt on economic growth was negative and significant in the long run. The impact of public debt on economic growth was negative but insignificant in the short run. In addition, the impact of ratio of debt servicing to GDP was significant and negative in the short and long run. There was no causality between public debt and economic growth. The study recommended that public authorities in Nigeria should reduce reliance on public debt and instead move towards increasing revenues through diversification of

the export base of the economy and expanding the tax net. The study also recommended strengthening public institutions so that revenues collected, in the form of debt or other means can be adequately utilized on investments that are efficient.

Kaka (2021), examined the existence of a mutual consensus on the effect of tax revenue and non-tax revenue on public debt in Nigeria. The study used documentary research design. Data was collected using secondary method of data collection from Debt Management office and Bureau of statistics and Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin data bank. Ordinary Least Square Multi regression model was used in analyzing the data. The research found out that there is a negative insignificant relationship between tax revenue, non-tax revenue and interest rate in relation to Nigerian public debt. Moreover, the study further found out that exchange rate and population rate had significant and positive relationship with Nigerian public debt.

Muhammad, Olaolu, Abu, and Umar (2021) examined the effect of public debt on inflation rate in Nigeria for the period 1985-2020 using ARDL technique to analyse the data. Findings showed that domestic debt had positive significant effect on inflation while external debt had no significant impact on inflation in Nigeria.

Omesi, Nkak., and Orlu (2021) examined the nexus between debt, debt service and economic growth: an empirical analysis of Nigeria economy with data ranging from 2012 to 2019 that was extracted from debt management office and statistical bulletin of Nigeria using regression analysis. Findings revealed that debt and debt servicing are not the factors behind economic growth in Nigeria. Furthermore, it was found that Internal and external, total debt servicing and inflation were on the increase.

Onyelle and Nwadike (2021) investigated the impact of national debt burden on economic stability in Nigeria. Data spanning 1981 to 2019 were collated from the World Development Indicators and Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, 2019 edition. Consequently, the variables used to measure debt burden were total debt-to-GDP ratio (debt overhang), short-term external debt-to-reserves ratio (reserve adequacy) and debt service cost-to-government revenue ratio (revenue adequacy) with exchange rate as a control variable, while economic stability was measured with real GDP growth rate. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was used for the analysis. The ARDL estimation showed that the explanatory variables collectively cause a diminishing impact on economic stability in the long run with revenue adequacy having a negative and significant impact. In the short run, all the components of debt burden, except debt overhang, had a negative and significant impact on economic stability.

Shuaibu *et al.* (2021) measured the impact of public debt on inflation and unemployment in Nigeria during the period 1985 to 2020. Autoregressive

Distributive Lag model (ARDL) Error Correction Model (ECM) were used for the analysis of the data. Unit root tests and Granger causality tests were also conducted to test the efficacy and predictive capability of the model. The findings of the study showed that long run relationship exists between public debt and unemployment in Nigeria. It shows that increase in public debt causes more unemployment, but that external debt causes more unemployment than domestic debt. But the results of cointegration analysis show absence of relationship between public debt and inflation.

Aiyedogbon *et al.* (2022) examined the short- and long-run impact of state debt on economic growth in Nigeria. The model was estimated using an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds testing method to cointegration for the long-run investigation. At the same time, the contemporaneous dynamics were explored using an unrestricted error correction model. The data were collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria's statistical bulletins and annual reports, and it spanned the years from 1990 to 2020. The study uncovers evidence of a long-term link between the study variables. In addition, the study found that all the explanatory variables were statistically significant. Specifically, economic growth was significant and negatively responsive to changes in external debt by 0.19% and debt servicing by 0.07%, contrary to its positive response to changes in domestic debt and exchange rate by 0.27% and 0.18%, respectively. The study recommended that government may consider more domestic borrowings to foreign borrowings that should only be resorted to when it is indispensable.

Ngangnchi, Joefendeh and Innocent (2022) investigated the extent to which external debt and public investment contribute to economic growth in Cameroon-emphasizing how public investment modulates the effect of external debt on economic growth. Time series data spanning the period 1980-2021 obtained from the World Bank's world development indicators were used, together with the Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) approach to ascertain the nature of the long-run relationship between external debt, public investment, and economic growth in Cameroon. Consistent with the debt-overhang and crowding-out literature, the study revealed a negative significant influence of external debt on economic growth in Cameroon. Results also revealed that there is a positive and significant direct effect of public investment on economic growth in the long run. Further results indicated that public investment and external debt positively and significantly affect engender economic growth in Cameroon.

The reviewed literatures show that there is no conformity in conclusion about the effect of public debt on observed macroeconomic variables. In addition, most of the study reviewed did not specifically address the effect of public debt on inflation. This study is an attempt at filling this gap.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted an *ex-post facto* design with the use of time series data for the period 2000-2021 based on data availability. This design was considered appropriate considering the fact that the data set used in the study were used as given. The variables used for the study are external debt, domestic debt, and inflation. While inflation is the dependent variable, domestic and external debt are the independent variables. The data for the study was obtained from CBN statistical bulletin 2021.

From the above, the study model is formulated as;

$$\text{Inf} = f(\text{DOD}, \text{EXTD}) \quad (1)$$

Where; Inf = inflation; DOD = domestic debt and EXTD = external debt.

Presenting equation (1) econometrically becomes;

$$\text{Inf} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{DOD} + \beta_2 \text{EXTD} + \mu \quad (2)$$

In Equation (2), other variables are as earlier explained, α_0 = intercept; β_1 and β_2 are the parameters; and μ is the error term. It is expected that β_1 and β_2 will be positive.

The data obtained were estimated using ordinary least square estimation technique in linear form using Eview 12. The interpretation was based on the Eview output.

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Trend Analysis

Figure 1: Inflation, domestic debt and external Debt in Nigeria (2000-2021).

Source: Author's presentation

The Figure 1 above shows the relationship between the variables of study (inflation, domestic debt and external debt) for a period of 22 years (2000-2021). From the figure, it can be seen that while the rate of inflation seems to be stable over time, domestic debt is on the consistent rise. At first, the external debts rose to 5 billion then drop in 2006 and remain at a relatively low profile between 2006 -2010 when it began

to rise steadily between 2010 and 2015. From 2016, external debt has been on a consistent rise. The drop in external debt in 2006 is probably due to debt pay back or cancellation obtained by Nigeria from communities of lenders especially Paris and London clubs. A gradual rise in external debt was again witnessed during the 2010-2015 period. It assumes a continuous rise from 2016 till date.

What is also observed from the figure is that, at first, domestic debt was lower than the external debt. But with the debt buy back of 2006, it is noticed that, there had been consistent rise in the domestic debts perhaps with a view to avoiding high interest payment associated with external debts. The most important thing as noticed from the figure is that, even with the rise in both the domestic and external debt, the rate of inflation seems to remain stable.

Table 1: Correlation Matrix between Inflation, Domestic Debts and External Debts

	DOD	EXTD	INF
DOD	1.000	0.7658	0.3266
EXTD	0.7658	1.000	0.5618
INF	0.3266	0.5618	1.000

Source: Author's computation

The correlation matrix presented in the Table 1 above shows that there is a positive weak relation between domestic debts and inflation and a positive moderate relation between external debt and inflation. The correlation indicates that inflation can be influence by both domestic and external debts.

Table 2: Effect of Public Debt on Inflation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-stat	Probability
C	11.51519	1.23890	9.294629	0.0000
DOD	-0.000196	0.000226	-0.865988	0.3973
EXTD	0.000799	0.000307	2.604305	0.0174

$R^2 = 0.34$: $Adj. R^2 = 0.27$ $DW = 2.17$

Source: Author's computation using Eview 12.

From the result on the Table 2 above, it can be established that there is a negative non-significant relationship between domestic debt and inflation in Nigeria. Consequently, the result indicates a positive significant relationship between external debt and inflation in Nigeria.

From the result, it can be deduced that, an increase in domestic debt will invariably reduce inflation. This is very apt giving the fact that inflation is a monetary phenomenon. Also, depending on the source of the domestic debt, domestic debt can bring about a reduction in inflation. If the government for instance uses monetary policy instrument like treasury bills, CBN ways and means and bonds which are both short term and long-term monetary instruments, the amount of money withdrawn from the economy within the period of borrowing could affect the purchasing power of the people adversely and this may bring about reduction in inflation. Thus, this result can be seen as appropriate except that the non-significance of it which make its economic interpretation invalid.

External debt on the other hand has a positive and significant relationship with inflation. The effect of this is that a percentage change in external debt will bring about very infinitesimal increase in the rate of inflation. What can be deduced from this finding is that, if external borrowing is channeled towards projects or infrastructural development, this will have ripple effect on the economy in terms of employment and aggregate demand. Thus increase in aggregate demand as a result of increase employment is likely to increase the rate of inflation in the economy. This finding no doubt supports the Keynesian theory on public debt that increase in government expenditure through public works will result in increase in aggregate demand.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Public debt and inflation have continuously and consistently spark debate in Nigeria and other developing economies as to their relationship with the other. While some believe that public debt sparks inflationary spiral, others believe otherwise. It is obvious that there is no conformity in findings as to the effect of public debts on inflation either in the short run or in the long run. It should be admitted also that, depending on how public debts are managed, the effect could be inflationary or deflationary. Thus, policy framework associated with a given debt could be a force either in positive or negative direction towards price stabilization. From the present study, it can be said that domestic debts could be very appropriate in managing inflation in an economy because it could in a way reduces the amount of money in circulation. This is not to say it is a cure-all for inflation. Again, external debts should be considered appropriate if there are life changing and sustaining projects to invest on. In view of the findings of this study, it suggested that government should consider domestic debt as the best bet because the cost of management is relatively cheaper in connection to external debts. Furthermore, institutional framework should be strengthened to ensure that in the case of external debts, the proceeds are properly channeled to ensure jobs creation and improvement in people living standards.

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